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Physicochemical Parameters and Trace Elements (TEs) Level in Top Soil from Selected Communities in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The ongoing rise in urban development has resulted in a surge in human activities, which has contributed to pollution, including the presence of potentially harmful elements. The study aims to evaluate the physicochemical parameters and trace elements (TEs) levels in top soil from selected communities in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. Five (5) composite soil samples were collected from five selected communities (Asipa, Lisa, Efuye, Ilarun and Dangbogboru) in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. The physicochemical analysis and TE estimation were performed using standard methods. The results revealed that all the investigated physicochemical parameters (soil moisture %, Bulk Density, % porosity, organic carbon and matter %, sand, clay and silt %, sodium, potassium, calcium and magnesium level), including the trace element such as Copper (Cu), Manganese (Mn), Zinc (Zn), Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd) and Cobalt (Co) concentrations comply with European Union standards. Consequently, it can be concluded that there was no trace element pollution in the soil at the time of the study.

Keywords: Physicochemical parameters, Trace Elements, Top Soil, Communities, Abeokuta

1. INTRODUCTION

Soil is an essential natural resource that plays a crucial role in supporting plant life, maintaining environmental balance, and contributing to various human activities. The quality of soil is determined by its physicochemical properties and the concentration of trace elements (TEs), which can influence its suitability for agriculture, human habitation, and environmental sustainability. Physicochemical parameters such as pH, organic matter content, cation exchange capacity, and electrical conductivity are critical indicators of soil health and fertility. Meanwhile, trace elements, which include both essential nutrients like iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), and copper (Cu), as well as potentially toxic elements such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), and mercury (Hg), can significantly impact soil quality (Akinola *et al.*, 2017).

Abeokuta, the capital of Ogun State in southwestern Nigeria, is a rapidly growing urban center characterized by a mix of agricultural, industrial, and residential activities. The diverse land use practices in this region have raised concerns about the quality of top soil and the potential contamination by trace elements due to anthropogenic activities such as waste disposal, industrial emissions, and agricultural inputs (Ojo *et al.*, 2019). The presence of trace elements in soils, especially at elevated concentrations, poses significant environmental and health risks. Accumulation of toxic elements in the soil can result in their uptake by crops, leading to food contamination and long-term health problems for local populations (Adekola & Akanbi, 2020).

In recent years, rapid urbanization, industrialization, and agricultural activities in Abeokuta, Ogun State, have raised concerns about the degradation of soil quality and the accumulation of potentially harmful trace elements. Waste disposal practices, industrial emissions, and the use of fertilizers and pesticides have been identified as major contributors to soil contamination in the region (Ojo *et al.*, 2019). These activities may lead to elevated levels of toxic trace elements, which can persist in soils for long periods, affecting crop productivity and human health through the food chain.

The problem of trace element contamination in topsoil is particularly concerning because many communities in Abeokuta rely on the soil for agricultural production. Elevated levels of toxic trace elements such as lead, cadmium, and mercury can accumulate in crops, leading to food contamination and long-term health effects such as neurological disorders, cancer, and kidney damage (Adekola & Akanbi, 2020). Additionally, the degradation of physicochemical properties such as soil pH and organic matter content can result in reduced agricultural productivity, threatening food security in the region.

Trace elements (copper, selenium and zinc) are nutritionally essential elements at low levels but toxic at higher levels, and others (lead, chromium, arsenic and mercury) have no known biological function. Studies has shown that chronic exposure to soil with Pb for example can cause mental lapses, nervous system and kidney damage, learning disabilities, poor muscle coordination, hearing damage, hypertension and decreased muscle and bone growth while Cr and Cd can be carcinogenic.

Given the potential risks to human health and the environment, there is an urgent need to evaluate the physicochemical parameters and trace element levels in topsoil from selected communities in Abeokuta. This study aims to identify the extent of soil contamination, assess the environmental risks, and provide valuable data for soil management and remediation efforts. Addressing this problem will help to ensure sustainable agricultural practices and mitigate the adverse effects of soil contamination on human health.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Description of the Study Area

The research study was conducted in Abeokuta, located at coordinates $7^{\circ}9'39''\text{N}$ and $3^{\circ}20'54''\text{E}$, which is known as the largest city and the capital of Ogun State, Nigeria (Map 1). This city is positioned on the eastern side of the Ogun River, close to a collection of rocky formations in a wooded savanna, 77 kilometers (48 miles) north of Lagos by railway, or 130 kilometers (81 miles) by water. According to the 2006 census, Abeokuta and its surrounding regions had a population of 449,088.

The area falls within Nigeria's rainforest zone and experiences a tropical climate characterized by distinct wet and dry seasons, with a dry season lasting approximately 130 days. It has a high population density, exceeding 500 individuals per hectare. The map of Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria is showed in Figure 1, while the communities selected for this study is presented in Table 1.

Figure 1. Map of Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria.

Table 1. Selected Communities and their geographical location.

Communities	Coordinates
Agodo	7°06'16.5"N 3°24'02.7"E
Asipa	7°02'41.0"N 3°16'20.3"E
Dagbagbaru	7°08'36.8"N 3°14'13.8"E
Efuye	7°03'40.7"N 3°24'07.7"E
Ilarun	7°09'03.1"N 3°14'18.1"E
Lisa	7°12'24.5"N 3°17'08.0"E

2. 2. Sampling

For the purpose of the study, five (5) composite soil samples were collected from five selected communities (Asipa, Lisa, Efuye, Ilarun and Dangbogboru) in Abeokuta, Ogun state Nigeria (Plates 1-5). The soils were collected into a sterile polythene sampling bag then transported to Tetra Laboratory, Abeokuta, Ogun state, Nigeria. At the laboratory the soil was sieved using 1000 µm sieve to remove dirt and larger particles. Then stored for digestion process

2. 3. Estimation of Soil profile

Soil physical parameters were determined using soil quality meter while mineral elements comprising of organic matter, sodium, calcium, potassium and magnesium were determined according to the method described by Oyelola *et al.* (2014) with some modifications. Exactly 2.0 g of each of the processed samples was weighed and subjected to dry ashing in a well-cleaned porcelain crucible at 550 °C in a muffle furnace. The resultant ash was dissolved in 5.0 ml of HNO₃/HCl/H₂O (1:2:3) and heated gently on a hot plate until brown fumes disappeared. To the remaining material in each crucible, 5.0 ml of de-ionized water was added and heated until a colourless solution was obtained. The mineral solution in each crucible was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask by filtration through Whatman No.42 filter paper and the volume was made to the mark with deionized water. The mineral elements were determined using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS). Organic carbon was determined using the LECO induction furnace carbon analyser.

2. 4. Acid Digestion and Metal Estimation

The *Aqua-regia* digestion method was employed the digestion proces. Exactly 1g of each soil sample was transferred into a 25 mls concentration of Nitric acid (HNO₃), Hydrochloric acid (HCl) in the ratio 1:3 respectively. The mixture was gently stirred to make a

homogenous mixture and was heated subsequently in a fume cupboard until the sample evaporated to about 15 ml. The samples were later cooled off, filtered and diluted with distilled water to a volume of 50 ml. The diluted samples were analyzed using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (ASS) for the present and concentration of heavy metals. Collected data are presented in Tables and charts using MS Excel 2016.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The physicochemical parameters of soil samples collected from the various selected communities is encapsulated in Figures 2-13, while the toxic element concentration is detailed in Table 2.

3. 1. Physicochemical Parameters

The highest percentage of soil moisture was recorded in Dangbogboru (29.66 %) while the lowest was in Ilarun (8.75 %). The highest soil Bulk Density was recorded in Ilaru (1.60 g/ml) while the lowest was equally in Asipa and Dangbogboru (1.50 g/ml). The highest percentage of soil porosity was recorded in Dangbogboru (43.30 %) while the lowest was in Asipa (0.43 %). The highest percentage of soil organic carbon was recorded in Asipa (2.23 %) while the lowest was in Ilaru (0.40 %). The highest percentage of soil organic matter was recorded in Asipa (3.85 %) while the lowest was in Ilaru (0.69 %). The highest percentage of sand was recorded in Lisa (88.24 %) while the lowest was in Asipa (82.80 %).

Figure 2. Soil moisture content across communities.

Figure 3. Bulk density across communities.

Figure 4. Soil porosity across communities.

Figure 5. Soil organic carbon % across communities.

Figure 6. Soil organic matter % across communities.

Figure 7. Sand % across communities.

Figure 8. Clay % across communities.

Figure 9. Silt % across communities.

Figure 10. Sodium concentration across communities.

Figure 11. Potassium concentration across communities.

Figure 12. Calcium concentration across communities.

Figure 13. Magnesium concentration across communities.

The highest percentage of clay was recorded in Asipa (12.64 %) while the lowest was equal in Efuye and Dangbogboru (7.64 %). The highest percentage of silt was recorded in Lisa (8.00 %) while the lowest was equal in Asipa (4.50 %). The highest sodium level was recorded in Asipa (0.35 cmol/kg) while the lowest was equal in Lisa and Ilaru (0.31 cmol/kg). The highest potassium level was recorded in Lisa (488.67 cmol/kg) while the lowest was equal in Ilaru (0.51 cmol/kg). The highest calcium level was recorded in Asipa (0.33 cmol/kg) while the lowest was equal in Lisa (0.29 cmol/kg). The highest magnesium level was recorded in Asipa (0.39 cmol/kg) while the lowest was equal in Lisa and Ilaru (0.33 cmol/kg).

3. 2. Trace Elements Level

The concentration of Copper (Cu), Manganese (Mn), Zinc (Zn), Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd), Cobalt (Co), and in the selected top soil were all below the compared international soil guideline values is presented in Table 2. The highest concentration of Cu was recorded in Efuye (1.46 mg/kg) while the lowest was in Ilarun (1.22 mg/kg). The concentration of Cu in soil across the selected communities are within the EU standard (140 mg/kg). The concentration recorded in the soil was lower than the report from Dhaka, Bangladesh (82.0 mg/kg, Islam *et al.* 2015), Lagos, Nigeria (8.0 mg/kg, Famuyiwa, *et al.*, 2018) but higher than the report from Oyo (0.01 mg/kg, Nwosu *et al.*, 2021) and Delta state (0.66 mg/kg, Osakwe, 2014)

The highest concentration of Mn was recorded in Lisa (1.96 mg/kg) while the lowest was in Ilarun (1.55 mg/kg). The concentration of Mn in soil across the selected communities are

within the EU standard (200 mg/kg). The concentration recorded in the soil was lower than the report from Ikorodu, Lagos (154 kg/kg; Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2021) and Accra, Ghana (391 mg/kg; Lawal *et al.*, 2015). The highest concentration of Zn was recorded in Efuye (2.36 mg/kg) while the lowest was in Ilarun (2.09 mg/kg). The concentration of Zn in soil across the selected communities are within the EU standard (300 mg/kg). The concentration recorded in the soil was lower than the report from Ikorodu, Lagos (328 mg/kg; Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2021) and Accra, Ghana (343 mg/kg; Lawal *et al.*, 2015).

The highest concentration of Pb was recorded in Efuye (2.14 mg/kg) while the lowest was in Dangbogboru (1.99 mg/kg). The concentration of Pb in soil across the selected communities are within the EU standard (400 mg/kg). The concentration recorded in the soil is lower than the concentration of various studies such as Cracow, Poland (49.0 mg/kg, Aleksander-Kwaterczak and Rajca 2015) and Accra, Ghana (121 mg/kg, Lawal *et al.*, 2015). The highest concentration of Cd was recorded in Efuye (1.48 mg/kg) while the lowest was in Dangbogboru (1.01 mg/kg). The concentration of Cd in soil across the selected communities are within the EU standard (3.00 mg/kg). The concentration recorded in the soil is lower than the concentration of various studies such as Automobile workshop in Abeokuta, Nigeria (80.0 mg/kg) and Steel fabricating workshops, Nigeria (45.5 mg/kg).

The highest concentration of Co was recorded in Efuye (3.68 mg/kg) while the lowest was in Dangbogboru (3.11 mg/kg). The concentration of Co in soil across the selected communities are within the EU standard (140 mg/kg). The concentration of Co was higher than the report from Oyo, Nigeria (0.03 mg/kg, Nwosu *et al.*, 2021) but largely lower than that of Akure, Ondo (80.7 mg/kg; Oguntimehin and Ipinmoroti, 2008).

Table 2. Heavy metals concentration compared to international soil standards.

HMs (mg/kg)	Asipa	Lisa	Efuye	Ilarun	Dangbogboru	EU Standard
Cu	1.33	1.43	1.46	1.22	1.31	140
Mn	1.79	1.96	1.81	1.55	1.71	200
Zn	2.22	2.26	2.36	2.09	2.11	300
Pb	2.10	2.08	2.14	2.01	1.99	400
Cd	1.11	1.14	1.48	1.31	1.01	3.00
Co	3.19	3.57	3.68	3.28	3.11	140

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4. 1. Conclusion

This study examines the physicochemical parameters and trace element levels in soil samples collected from various communities in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. Five soil samples were gathered and analyzed using standard methodologies. The results indicate that

the investigated parameters, including trace element concentrations, comply with European Union standards. Consequently, it can be concluded that there was no trace element pollution in the soil at the time of the study.

4. 2. Recommendation

Based on the study, it is recommended that

- ✓ It is advisable that a continuous monitoring of the soil should be employed.
- ✓ An appropriate disposal practices should be carried on and around the soil.

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Pictorial Views of the Top Soil from Selected Communities in Abeokuta

Plate 1. Asipa Community.

Plate 2. Lisa Community.

Plate 3. Efuye Community.

Plate 4. Ilarun Community.

Plate 5. Dangbogboru Community.